

TRANSFORMATIONS IN THE WORLD OF WORK AND EDUCATIONAL PUBLIC POLICY IN BRAZIL ¹

Changes in the world of work and educational public policy in Brazil

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to question the proposal to invest in human capital as a solution to the imminent structural unemployment resulting from the adoption of new robotics and artificial intelligence technologies published in 2018 by the World Bank. Based on (1) an empirical analysis of the Brazilian labor market from the perspective of the evolution of the working class's educational credentials, (2) the impacts of new technologies on work, and (3) the challenges arising from the metamorphoses experienced by the working class, the article concludes that it is timely to reflect on an alternative public education policy that aims to develop a critical understanding of Brazilian society, taking into account not only training for work, but also for social and political action.

Keywords: Work. Education. Public Policy.

Resumo

O presente artigo objetiva questionar a proposta de investimento em capital humano como uma solução para o iminente desemprego estrutural decorrente da adoção das novas tecnologias da robótica e da inteligência artificial publicada em 2018 pelo Banco Mundial. Tendo por base (1) a análise empírica do mercado de trabalho brasileiro a partir da perspectiva da evolução das credenciais educacionais da classe trabalhadora, (2) os impactos das novas tecnologias sobre o trabalho e (3) os desafios decorrentes das metamorfoses vivenciadas pela classe-que-vive-do-trabalho, o artigo conclui ser oportuna a reflexão sobre uma alternativa de política pública educacional que tenha por propósito o desenvolvimento de uma compreensão crítica da sociedade brasileira, levando em consideração não apenas a formação para o trabalho, mas, também para a atuação social e política.

Palavras-chave: Trabalho. Educação. Política Pública.

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1. INTRODUCTION

At the end of 2018, the World Bank, in its World Development Report (WDR) entitled "The Changing Nature of Work," presents its view on the public policies to be adopted by governments in order to prepare their populations for the imminent changes in the world of work resulting from the integration of new artificial intelligence and robotics technologies in the production of goods and services. Seeking to reassure the working class about the future, the document classifies concerns about such changes as unfounded, pointing to the creation of new types of work for which public policies in the field of technical education should qualify people. *Investing in human capital is the priority to make the most of this evolving economic opportunity* (World Bank, 2018, p. 3).

With a view to contributing to this debate, this article aims to question the World Bank's proposal and present a possible embryonic idea for an alternative public education policy. This is developed throughout the text, based on three processes: (1) analysis of the insertion of Brazilian workers into the country's labor market from the perspective of their educational credentials, using data from the IBGE's National Household Sample Survey (PNAD) for the period from 2001 to 2015⁴; (2) the view presented by Teles and Caldas (2019) on the impacts on work resulting from the adoption of new technologies; and (3) the debate between Figueiras and Cavalcante (2019) and Standing (2015) on the current transformations in the world of work.

Mirroring this methodological approach, the article is structured in three parts, in addition to this introduction and the final considerations. The first part identifies the main transformations in Brazil's workforce in terms of qualifications based on the completion of years of study between 2001 and 2015. This longer section of the text seeks to identify the extent to which, as proclaimed by Human Capital Theory, the expectation of better integration into the world of work was met due to the increase in the educational credentials of Brazilian workers. It is divided into five subparts: (a) an overview of the evolution of the economically active population (EAP)⁵; (b) the behavior of its two subsets - employed and unemployed; (c) the employed population, according to the five most important occupational positions (employee, domestic worker, self-employed, employer, and unpaid); (d) the process of flexibilization of forms of labor contracting; and (e) evolution of labor remuneration.

In the second part, it discusses verified and feared impacts on work resulting from the adoption of new technologies. In the third section, based on the debate about a supposed new farewell to work, it presents how the arguments

⁴ As the newest methodology of the National Household Sample Survey (PNAD Continua) only began to be applied to data collected from 2012 onwards, we chose to work with the PNAD historical series for the period from 2001 to 2015, which covers a broader time frame.

⁵ New nomenclatures were defined by the International Labor Organization during the 19th International Conference of Labor Statisticians, held in 2013, and have already been adopted by the Continuous National Household Sample Survey (PNAD Continua). However, in order to maintain conceptual rigor, it was imperative to adopt the PNAD categories categories (see National Household Sample Survey - Methodological Notes, available at: ftp://ftp.ibge.gov.br/Trabalho_e_Rendimento/Pesquisa_Nacional_por_Amostra_de_Domicilios_anual/microdados/2015/Metodologia_2017_0517.zip).

presented reinforce the rhetoric about the need for labor deregulation.

2. MARKET WORK AND CREDENTIALS EDUCATIONAL FROM WORKFORCE IN BRAZIL

Over the last three decades, the Brazilian labor market has undergone transformations, *pari passu* with changes experienced in the country's economic and political plans, which, since the 1990s, have accelerated its process of integration into global productive and financial systems (ALVES, 2007; ANTUNES, 2005; POCHMANN, 2002 and 2008). Driven by the waves of unemployment experienced during this period, competition among workers seeking the best opportunities for employment, a phenomenon typical of such situations, as predicted by Offe and Hinrichs (1989, pp. 61-66), intensified, strengthening the pursuit of qualifications through education as a competitive strategy for workforce differentiation. In fact, one of the most significant changes that can be highlighted in the national labor market is the increase in the amount of time dedicated to studies by individuals in the working population, a phenomenon that, as will be seen from the data analyzed here, occurred specifically in the first fifteen years of the 21st century.

2.1 Overview of the workforce in Brazil in recent years

When analyzing PNAD data on the classification of large Brazilian population subgroups in relation to the labor market, it can be seen that the EAP grew by 24.3% between 2001 and 2015 (Table 1). As this increase was smaller than that observed in the subset that contains it (the Working Age Population – PIA), the participation rate for that period fell by 1.8%, from 60.5% to 59.4%. However, when evaluating the time frame in 5-year (or 6-year, between 2009 and 2015) segments, growth can be observed between 2001 and 2005 (4.0%), a slight reduction from 2005 to 2009 (1.3%), and, from 2009 onwards, a more accelerated decline, which by 2015 was 4.3%, countered in 2014, when the indicator grew 2.2% compared to the previous year (Table 1).

Table 1 - Evolution of population distribution in relation to the labor market - Brazil, 2001, 2005, 2009, and 2015

Ano	Populações						TX. Part.	Tx. Desocup.
	Total	PIA	PNEA	PEA	Ocupados	Desocupados		
2001	172.742.385	140.404.412	55.518.148	84.886.264	76.936.438	7.949.826	60,5%	9,4%
2002	175.076.603	143.121.597	55.371.774	87.749.823	79.708.522	8.041.301	61,3%	9,2%
2003	177.360.349	145.742.796	56.258.084	89.484.712	80.775.414	8.709.298	61,4%	9,7%
2004	183.439.253	150.845.950	57.282.163	93.563.787	85.245.933	8.317.854	62,0%	8,9%
2005	185.651.425	153.722.254	57.040.208	96.682.046	87.695.271	8.986.775	62,9%	9,3%
2006	187.851.823	156.758.044	58.898.251	97.859.793	89.636.973	8.222.820	62,4%	8,4%
2007	189.953.924	159.411.395	60.512.220	98.899.175	90.854.655	8.044.520	62,0%	8,1%
2008	191.999.849	162.266.233	61.679.940	100.586.293	93.420.362	7.165.931	62,0%	7,1%
2009	193.995.123	164.640.165	62.359.292	102.280.873	93.783.537	8.497.336	62,1%	8,3%
2011	197.825.297	169.211.451	67.625.798	101.585.653	94.763.220	6.822.433	60,0%	6,7%
2012	199.688.907	171.035.897	68.572.836	102.463.061	96.100.290	6.362.771	59,9%	6,2%
2013	201.467.084	173.132.594	69.731.130	103.401.464	96.659.379	6.742.085	59,7%	6,5%
2014	203.190.852	175.234.405	68.409.995	106.824.410	99.447.612	7.376.798	61,0%	6,9%
2015	204.860.101	177.656.822	72.137.391	105.519.431	95.380.483	10.138.948	59,4%	9,6%

Source: National Household Sample Survey (PNAD/IBGE), 2001-2009 and 2011-2015

These variations in participation rates resulted from changes in the labor market scenario, which in turn reflected the dynamics of the country's economy. Thus, during periods of economic downturn or slow growth, such as between 2001 and 2003, high unemployment rates were maintained and there was a concomitant increase in the participation rate, which represents demographic pressure on the labor market (Table 1). The period of highest growth in the participation rate, between 2001 and 2005, corresponds to the same period in which the unemployment rate remained at higher levels. In fact, it was only as unemployment fell successively from 2006 onwards, i.e., after the economy consolidated successive real increases, that there was a reduction in the participation rate (Table 1).

Looking at this workforce from the perspective of its distribution by years of schooling, the evolution of its numbers shows an intense search for higher education on the part of the workforce. In 2001, the two classes with the least amount of schooling, added to those with no schooling, i.e., the contingent of individuals who had completed at most the first seven years of the formal education system, accounted for more than half of the EAP (54.1%), while the latter two, i.e., individuals with eleven or more years of schooling, accounted for 28.6% of the EAP. By 2015, this reality had practically reversed. This is because the first group now accounted for 31.2% of the EAP, and those with higher educational credentials had grown to more than half of the workforce, accounting for 51.5% of it (Table 2).

Table 2 - Evolution of the distribution of the economically active population and participation rate by years of schooling, Brazil - 2001, 2005, 2009, and 2015

Variable/Category	2001		2005		2009		2015	
	PEA	Dist. Part. Tx.	PEA	Dist. Part. Tx.	PEA	Dist. Part. Tx.	PEA	Dist. Part. Tx.
Years of Study	100.0%	60.5	100.0	62.4	100.0	62.4	100.0	59.4
No education	11.1	52.9	9.1	52.6	7.5	48.0	5.7	39.8
From 1 to 3 years	13.5	49.4	11.2	50.0	8.9	43.7	6.4	37.3
From 4 to 7 years	29.5	53.9	26.8	54.0	23.1	51.2	19.1	45.8
From 8 to 10 years	16.9	65.2	17.4	66.8	17.2	64.9	17.3	59.7
11 to 14 years old	21.9	78.1	27.6	80.5	33.0	80.1	37.7	76.3
15 or more years	6.7	85.3	7.6	85.6	10.1	85.1	13.8	82.0
Not determined	0.4	70.3	0.3	73.1	0.2	70.4	0.1	62.2
Not reported	0.0	-	0.0	-	0.0	-	0.0%	-

Source: National Household Sample Survey (PNAD/IBGE), 2001-2009 and 2011-2015

Internally, too, among individuals with less education, between 2001 and 2015, they gradually began to enter the labor market in relatively smaller numbers. This can be seen in the 24.9% drop in the participation rate of individuals with no education, which fell from 52.9% to 39.8%, and in the 24.5% drop in this indicator for individuals with 1 to 3 years of schooling, which fell from 49.4% to 37.3%. In other words, people of working age increasingly chose to enter the labor market as they extended their accumulated time in education. This process was further corroborated, mainly from 2005 onwards, by the improvement in the country's economic dynamics, which grew on average (3.95% per annum) between that year and 2011, a fact that had a positive impact on the level of employment.

2.2 Evolution of (un)employment according to length of study

In terms of study time, it is commonly believed that the more an individual dedicates to their studies, the greater and better their opportunities for entering the job market. When tested against Brazilian unemployment rate data from 2001 to 2015, this reasoning proves to be only partially true, since, among the three groups with the longest study time, only in the workforce of individuals with fifteen or more years of education was the unemployment rate lower than the overall unemployment rate (Graph 1). Compared to the rate observed in 2001, unemployment rose by 32.4% for the stratum with the highest educational credentials, jumping from 3.7% to 4.9% in 2015.

Considering that, currently, the formal education system defines the minimum length of elementary school as nine years and high school as three more years, in order to enter this stratum of the EAP, where unemployment is lower, an individual needs to take a higher education course. Among those who completed 8 to 10 years of schooling, having completed elementary school at most, the rate was at its highest levels, on average 49.7% higher than the overall unemployment rates recorded in Table 1. To a lesser extent, but still above the overall average, unemployment affected the stratum of people with 11 to 14 years of schooling, with rates 0.6 to 1.5 percentage points higher.

Graph 1 – Evolution of the unemployment rate by years of education – Brazil – 2001, 2005, 2009, and 2015

Source: IBGE/PNAD

From another perspective, that of the universe of employed individuals, PNAD data clearly show the increase in the level of education of this population group (Graph 2).

Graph 2 - Evolution of the relative distribution of employment by years of study - Brazil - 2001, 2005, 2009, and 2015

Source: IBGE/PNAD

The portion with 11 or more years of schooling, which had at least completed high school in 2001, accounted for less than one-third of the total (30.0%); in 2015, it accounted for more than half (53.2%). On the other hand, the subset of individuals with up to 7 years of schooling, which in 2001 accounted for 53.4% of the employed population, fell by 44.0%, totaling 29.9% in the last year analyzed.

In addition to these facts, it is important to take into account the possible positions that workers have taken in the occupational universe. This is because, as will be seen below, an increasing number of years of completed education may not guarantee placement in a desired position. Each of the five most frequent occupational positions, when considered from the perspective of years of study, can better reveal this reality.

2.3 The universe of employed persons from the perspective of occupational position

When analyzing the evolution of the relative distribution of employment by position within the group, it can be seen that, among the five most significant categories – employee, domestic worker, self-employed, employer, and unpaid – between 2001 and 2015, two of them, namely employee and self-employed, showed positive variations (Graph 3).

Graph 3 – Evolution of the relative distribution of occupation by position held – Brazil – 2001, 2005, 2009, and 2015

Source: IBGE/PNAD

The number of employees grew by 11.2%, jumping from 54.3% to 60.4%; while the number of self-employed workers grew by 2.7%, from 22.3% to 22.9%. The other three categories saw a relative decline, with the most significant drop occurring among unpaid workers, who fell by 43.9%; domestic workers decreased by 15.4%, and employers by 11.9%.

Looking at the composition of the subset of employees from the perspective of years of schooling (Graph 4), significant changes were observed during the period analyzed: reductions in the share of those with up to 10 years of schooling and the opposite effect in the two subsets with the highest amount of schooling.

Graph 4 - Evolution of the relative distribution of the position occupied by employees by years of study – Brazil – 2001, 2005, 2009, and 2015

Source: IBGE/PNAD

Specifically, the proportion of workers with up to 10 years of schooling, which accounted for 60.9% of employees in 2001, fell to 37.5% in 2015. The percentage of individuals with 11 or more years of schooling jumped from 39.1% to 62.5%. This growth was due to increases of 93.6% in the percentage of individuals with 15 or more years of schooling and 49.0% in the percentage of employees with 11 to 14 years of schooling.

In relation to the level of education among those employed as domestic workers, there were clear signs of improvement, given that in 2001 only 7.0% had 11 or more years of schooling and 23.6% had 8 or more years. When the same assessment was made for 2015, it was found that the number of those with 11 or more years of schooling had more than tripled, reaching 24.3%; the share of domestic workers with 8 or more years of schooling almost doubled in size, jumping from 23.6% in 2001 to 46.7% of the domestic workforce in 2015 (Graph 5).

Graph 5 - Evolution of the relative distribution of domestic workers by years of schooling - Brazil - 2001, 2005, 2009, and 2015

Source: IBGE/PNAD

Although still low in percentage terms, it is important to highlight the statistical emergence of domestic workers with higher education levels, with 15 or more years of schooling, in what is proven to be one of the occupations with the most precarious working conditions. This class, which did not exist in 2001, accounted for 1.6% of the subset in question in 2015 (Graph 5).

In addition to domestic workers, another position in which job insecurity is present in various aspects is that of self-employed workers. In general,

Self-employed workers have longer working hours, lower incomes than those who are employed, are not covered by most social security institutions, are not members of associations or unions, and their working conditions are highly unstable (PAMPLONA, 2001, p. 119). Among their economic activities, one that currently best exemplifies this reality is that of Uber drivers, with flexible working hours and remuneration, no mandatory social security contributions, and total uncertainty as to whether they will be able to continue providing that service.

Between 2001 and 2015, the subset of self-employed workers, which had been declining until 2013, grew (Chart 3). The behavior of the variations in their share of total employment, even though not showing quantitatively similar changes, followed the same direction as the unemployment rate almost every year (Chart 6).

Graph 6 - Annual evolution of the unemployment rate and the share of the labor force in self-employment, Brazil, 2001-2015

Source: own elaboration

In fact, when testing the correlation between the data from these two indicators for the period studied, a strong positive relationship (0.817) was found between the variation in unemployment and the share of self-employment in the labor force, allowing us to conclude that this type of employment tends to grow with increases in the unemployment rate, although the reverse is not necessarily true, since the growth of the self-employed workforce reduces unemployment. The data reflect the reality that, when unemployment spreads, people find it more difficult to ensure their material reproduction. As a result, many of them are compelled to engage in some form of productive activity on their own account, especially in the informal sector, where the frequency of work activities and, consequently, income is irregular. This is, in fact, one of the faces of the process of job insecurity: camouflaging the phenomenon of unemployment.

Analyzing the composition of the self-employed workforce from the perspective of years of schooling, it can be observed that between 2001 and 2015, the proportion of those with 11 to 14 years of schooling more than doubled, increasing their share to 101.4%. The share of those with more years of schooling grew by 91.8%, jumping from 4.9% in 2001 to 9.4% in 2015 (Graph 7).

Graph 7 - Evolution of the relative distribution of self-employed positions by years of education – Brazil - 2001, 2005, 2009, and 2015

Source: IBGE/PNAD

Focusing on the assessment of the evolution of the occupational category with the lowest relative participation, that of employer, from the perspective of their length of study throughout the period studied, it can be seen that it brought together individuals with the best educational credentials (Graph 8). This is because more than half of employers had at least 11 years of schooling in 2001 (51.8%). By 2015, this share had increased to more than two-thirds (69.4%).

Graph 8 - Evolution of the relative distribution of employer positions by years of education – Brazil - 2001, 2005, 2009, and 2015

Source: IBGE/PNAD

Regarding the distribution of unpaid workers by years of schooling, although there was an increase in the proportion of people with more years of schooling during the period, the vast majority of these workers (68.4%) had up to 7 years of schooling in 2015 (Graph 9).

Graph 9 - Evolution of the relative distribution of unpaid positions by years of study - Brazil - 2001, 2005, 2009, and 2015

Source: IBGE/PNAD

In 2001, this educational weakness in formal terms was even more pronounced, as it corresponded to 82.7% of this subset of employed persons. To counterbalance this trend, the share with 11 or more years of schooling, which represented 7.0% of these workers in 2001, rose to 16.2% in 2015.

2.4 The flexibilization of work

Among the changes observed in employment in Brazil during the last decade of the 20th century, the informalization and flexibilization of forms of employment stand out. In this article, based on the experience of Schneider and Rodarte (2006, pp. 82-88) and IPEA, which, using data from PNAD, developed the indicator of the degree of informality of work (IPEADATA), we refer to flexible occupations as those that are not formally registered, self-employed, for own consumption, and unpaid, in order to analyze how the process of labor flexibility in Brazil unfolded between 2001 and 2015.

Looking at the evolution of flexible employment, there was a 17.3% drop in the first fifteen years of this century, from 57.9% of jobs in 2001 to 47.9% in 2015 (Table 3).

Table 3 - Evolution of the share of flexible employment in total employment, Brazil - 2001, 2005, 2009, and 2015

DISCRIMINAÇÃO	Ano			
	2001	2005	2009	2015
Ocupados	76.936.438	87.695.271	93.783.537	95.380.483
Ocupados flexibilizados	44.533.419	49.595.688	48.289.944	45.660.410
% de Ocupação flexibilizada	57,9%	56,6%	51,5%	47,9%

Source: PNAD/IBGE, 2001-2009 and 2011-2015

This is due to improved conditions resulting from the decline in unemployment until 2013 and increased oversight by the Ministry of Labor and Employment (MTE) (SIMÃO, 2009), corroborated, as of 2014, by the implementation of the Digital Tax Bookkeeping System, SPED Social, or eSocial. This system

has completely computerized and unified the ancillary labor declarations made by employers to various government agencies, facilitating the labor inspection process.

Alternating between reading the flexible occupations and the breakdown by years of study, there has been a significant increase in the percentage of the workforce with longer formal education (Table 4). Individuals with 11 to 14 years of schooling who were subject to flexible working conditions increased their participation by 103.8% between 2001 and 2015. At the same time, the workforce with higher levels of education increased its share from 3.4% to 8.0%—an increase of 135.3%.

Table 4- Evolution of the distribution of flexible employment by years of schooling, Brazil - 2001, 2005, 2009, and 2015

Anos de Estudo	Ano			
	2001	2005	2009	2015
Total	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%
Sem Instrução	16,6%	14,3%	12,3%	9,8%
De 1 a 3 anos	18,5%	16,0%	13,4%	10,7%
De 4 a 7 anos	33,5%	32,3%	29,7%	26,1%
De 8 a 10 anos	14,3%	16,1%	17,5%	18,2%
De 11 a 14 anos	13,3%	17,2%	21,6%	27,1%
15 ou mais anos	3,4%	3,9%	5,2%	8,0%
Não determinado	0,4%	0,3%	0,2%	0,2%

Source: PNAD/IBGE, 2001-2009 and 2011-2015

2.5 Worker income from the perspective of study time

When it comes to working conditions, income (the price of labor) is certainly the most significant indicator. Between 2001 and 2015, the working class saw an average increase of 33.3% (or 1.9% per annum) in their real monthly income. This growth process began primarily in 2005 (Table 5).

Table 5 - Annual evolution of average real monthly income, Brazil – 2001/2015

Ano	Rendimento Médio	
	Nominal	Real (1)
2001	R\$ 362,28	R\$ 903,87
2005	R\$ 521,28	R\$ 927,13
2009	R\$ 733,90	R\$ 1.096,82
2015	R\$ 1.204,71	R\$ 1.204,71

Source: PNAD/IBGE, 2001, 2005, 2009, and 2015

(1) At 2015 prices, based on the IPCA/IBGE

The evolution of real average monthly income when analyzed from the perspective of workers' years of study reveals at least two curious facts. The first refers to the decline in average incomes for the two classes with the most years of study (Table 6).

Table 6 - Annual evolution of real average monthly income by years of study, Brazil - 2001 to 2015

Year	Years Study					
	No education	1 to 3 years	From 4 to 7 years old	From 8 to 10 years old	From 11 to 14 years old	15 years or older
2001	R\$ 422.97	R\$ 384.70	R\$ 517.78	R\$ 734.16	R\$ 1,515.28	R\$ 5,098.36
2005	R\$ 493.71	R\$ 426.96	R\$ 520.55	R\$ 664.21	R\$ 1,329.39	R\$ 4,549.07
2009	R\$ 639.41	R\$ 502.72	R\$ 610.27	R\$ 762.76	R\$ 1,380.51	R\$ 4,328.41
2015	R\$ 784.48	R\$ 583.33	R\$ 670.42	R\$ 776.61	R\$ 1,333.01	R\$ 4,008.55

Source: IBGE/PNAD

The workforce with 15 or more years of schooling, which earned an average of R\$5,098.36 per month in 2001, ended 2015 with a real average monthly income of R\$4,008.55—a 21.4% reduction in purchasing power. A similar trend, but with a less intense decline, occurred in relation to the average monthly earnings of those who completed 11 to 14 years of schooling, which decreased by 12.0% between 2001 and 2015.

At the opposite end of the spectrum, among uneducated workers, due to the minimum wage appreciation policy, average monthly income saw its highest growth in the period under review (85.3%), meaning that in 2015, a person with less than one year of schooling earned on average slightly more than workers with up to 10 years of schooling (0.9%). In that year, an uneducated worker earned on average 17.0% more than a worker with 4 to 7 years of completed schooling. Their income was also 34.5% higher than that of workers with 1 to 3 years of schooling.

It is important to highlight the significant differences in income between workers with up to 10 years of schooling and those with 11 to 14 years of schooling, as well as between this group and those with higher levels of education. In 2015, on average, individuals who had completed high school or were close to that level earned around 71.5% more than those with up to 10 years of schooling. In the same year, workers who entered and completed higher education earned average monthly incomes three times higher than those who had completed up to 14 years of schooling.

When considering the historical process of social formation in Brazil and its labor market, marked by the legacy of slavery and neglect in relation to workforce training, it is imperative to highlight the phenomenon of the intense increase in the level of education of the Brazilian workforce at the beginning of the 21st century. To increase the chances of finding employment, the so-called market economy forces individuals to seek qualifications, without, however, guaranteeing them the desired job. Therefore, we see a reality that, in some respects, contradicts the established expectations that dedicating more time to studies would be synonymous with better integration into the labor market. Looking at the workforce from the perspectives of unemployment, the precariousness of employment contracts, and the income of the employed population, we find facts that are surprising to common sense.

In fact, the universe of occupations now consists mainly of people who have completed at least high school. This is a natural result, among other reasons, of the expansion of the labor force with this characteristic. Individuals who have completed 11 to 14 years of schooling, in particular, faced greater

competition, an unemployment rate above the general average, more flexible employment contracts, and a consequent downward trend in average income.

Unemployment was effectively lower among workers who entered higher education. The income of this class is on average significantly higher than the overall average (232.8%), although over the fifteen years analyzed, it fell by an amount that, in absolute terms (R\$ 1,089.82 less), approached the average income of the class immediately below it (R\$ 1,333.01).

Among the three groups with the longest periods of study, only workers with 15 or more years of study had an average unemployment rate below the overall average between 2001 and 2015. The other two, comprising individuals with 8 to 14 years of schooling, suffered the most from unemployment, more than workers with no education or those who completed up to 7 years of schooling.

The strategy of improving educational qualifications among workers translates into broader participation in the labor market and higher average incomes. However, although these incomes are higher, they decrease significantly in the two strata with higher educational qualifications, where flexible employment arrangements are also on the rise. Thus, in Brazil today, more education does not necessarily translate into lower unemployment rates or greater social security from employment contracts.

Some noteworthy facts revealed by PNAD data relate to uneducated workers. Within this subgroup of the population, the unemployment rate was the second lowest, the average wage increase in absolute terms was the highest, and participation in flexible occupations was the second lowest.

3. VERIFIED AND FEARED IMPACTS ON WORK

From the Industrial Revolution to the present day, technological advances have generated fear and questions about their effects on human labor. As in the days of the controversial inventions of the steam engine, combustion engines, the use of electricity, rapid transportation, and communications, today's innovations have recognized potential to reconfigure production processes, with significant gains in labor productivity, accompanied, consequently, by a reduction in the technical need for certain human skills incorporated by machines. As a result, the labor market is expected to undergo further changes, with a significant increase in structural unemployment and a redesign of the demand for labor.

Despite this justifiable fear, affecting workers from the most diverse levels of technical qualification and professions, Teles and Caldas (2019) draw attention to the fact that such fear is linked to a future event which, although possible, is still undefined in time and space, subject to influences of a sociopolitical nature. Predictions in this direction of large-scale structural unemployment made both by Marx (1996) in his critique of compensation theory and by Keynes (1963) in his concerns about our grandchildren have not come to pass, although "similar anticipations of massive technological unemployment [...] in the current debate on the 'future of work'" (CALDAS; TELES, 2019, p. 32).

In this regard, it is interesting to highlight a statement made by these authors that corroborates the conception of the embryo of a public education policy proposal that will be presented here. They state that:

Our assessment of the futures proposed to us, and our choice of those we desire (or wish to avoid) for our grandchildren, depend not only on uncertain predictions about the impact that 'new' technologies may have on employment, but also, fundamentally, on how we conceive of human labor and machines. Different conceptions of work carry with them opposing political implications (CALDAS; TELES, 2019, p. 32).

Therefore, already in the present, for reasons that are not typically technological, but essentially political, high structural unemployment, drastic reduction in social protection, persistent decline in labor income, and precarious working conditions characterize the contemporary world (TELES; CALDAS, 2019).

In this highly adverse environment for the working class, the emergence of companies that shape the phenomena of *the gig economy*, *sharing economy*, *crowdsourcing*, *on-demand economy*, platformization, uberization, and other terms is attributed a revolutionary character. The "great" transformations caused by the misnamed platform companies are, for many, unquestionable signs that employment is becoming extinct.

However, leaving this repeated rhetoric aside and analyzing the practical implications of the innovations in question, it can be said that their effect on the production process falls almost exclusively on the worker. For example, Uber, in technical terms, has not changed the core form of the service of how a driver picks up a passenger and transports them from one geographical point to another (TELES; CALDAS, 2019). The main change lies in the relationships established between the service provider (company), the service provider (driver), and the service contractor (passenger). The power exercised by each of the parties during the social relationship clearly reveals that the digital platform is not the company, but rather a tool used by it to first enable communication between the contractor and Uber, and between Uber and the driver; then to monitor the provision of the service; and finally to evaluate the performer and contractor. In addition, the value of the service provided and the share that each party is entitled to are defined by Uber. Finally, the transportation service company has the power to terminate the drivers registered with it at any time, without the need for clear justification. Similarly, with some variations due to the nature of the service offered, similar power relations are exercised by delivery, real estate rental, translation, and other service companies. Thus, the digital platform is in fact a business and work management tool (FILGUEIRAS; CAVALCANTE, 2018; ANTUNES; FILGUEIRAS, 2019). The algorithms programmed into them record, analyze, and guide decision-making based on the company's objectives. As a tool, it is far from representing a radical innovation in the way goods are produced or services are provided.

While, on the one hand, technology enables the development of new forms of work organization and management, on the other hand, the almost complete lack of regulation of

This activity, which can be interpreted as *laissez faire*, *laissez aller*, *laissez passer*, has a detrimental impact on the working and living conditions of the working class. With no greater rights to be respected by companies, the costs and risks inherent in the provision of services fall on workers (SLEE, 2017). With flexible working hours and remuneration, people are working more and more to earn less and less (ANTUNES, FILGUEIRAS, 2019).

4. ARMED THE DEREGULATION OF LABOR WITH "NEW" ARGUMENTS

The recent history of labor studies records two moments in which theories were proposed that suggest the disappearance of workers as a social class and central category of analysis of the dynamics of the capitalist way of life and production. The first of these was in the 1980s, when Gorz (1982) presented his "Farewell to the Proletariat" and Offe (1989) questioned the centrality of work as a key category in sociology. In this first debate, this proposition found its counterpoint in the studies presented in the mid-1990s by Antunes (2006; 2009), indicating that it was essential to understand the transformations that the working class was undergoing.

The second moment, very recent, stems from Standing's (2015) proposal that a new social class, the precariat, is in the process of forming, reflecting the construction of a global market society that would result in a new social class structure, in which the working class would cease to exist as a class unit, splitting into distinct new classes. More than two decades after his *Adeus ao proletariado? (Farewell to the proletariat?)*, Antunes (2018, pp. 63-64), after analyzing Standing's conceptual suggestions, states:

[...] we are challenged to understand its new polysemy [of the working class], its new morphology, whose most visible element is its multifaceted design, which brings out so many transversalities between class, generation, gender, ethnicity, etc. [...] This new morphology comprises not only the working class inherited from the Taylorist and Fordist era, [...] but must also include the new precarious service proletariat, an integral and growing part of the working class.

In the same vein, Filgueiras and Cavalcanti (2018), evaluating Standing's theoretical proposal, show that it is the result of a relatively superficial observation of the contemporary reality of work which, in the field of appearances, seen from the legal perspective of the contractual link between capital and labor, the delimitation of working hours, and the prior definition of wage values, seems to deconstruct the working class. However, if we observe its essential characteristics of wage labor, subordination, and the consequent asymmetry of power between capital and labor, we see that a significant portion of the changes experienced by workers result from the flexibilization of the parameters that define the contractual relationship, which did not exist at the beginning of the formation of the labor market with the advent of the Industrial Revolution and which were gradually achieved over a period of about 150 years.

⁶ Let it be, let it go, let it pass, the motto of classical economic liberalism, inherited by the neoclassical school of economics.

These researchers emphasize that the pseudo-inexorability of the process of dismantling regulations protecting the working class feeds into the narrative of a “new farewell to the working class.” Faced with a resurgence of discourse on the redesign of the social class structure in the current context of the use of new technological tools for work management, it is argued that, despite efforts to deny employment relationships, new forms of work continue to be predominantly salaried, with remuneration no longer predefined by a workday, but rather for each microtask performed, thus taking the form defined by Marx as piecework wages. Admitting that there are indeed changes in work management on the part of companies, this process integrates strategies to conceal the wage relationship with a view to reducing alternatives that limit the exploitation of labor. This is because, as Marx (2017, p. 624) states, “given piecework wages, it is natural that the worker’s interest is to employ his labor power as intensively as possible, which makes it easier for the capitalist to raise the normal degree of intensity.”

To demonstrate this fact, four central arguments are presented. The first, based on statistical series covering more than two decades, asserts that wage labor has grown worldwide, according to aggregate data covering the last few decades. The second argues that so-called new forms of work, which treat workers as independent producers, partners, associates, etc., are nothing more than work management strategies that increase the flexibility of their institutions and their precariousness, denying the employment relationship itself in order to undermine social limits on labor exploitation. The third, also statistically based, indicates that variations in real or disguised self-employment are strongly linked to labor market performance and social labor regulations. The fourth denounces that the narrative of the “new farewell to the proletariat” strengthens the strategy of capital’s gain of power, making work more precarious and unable to oppose the current levels of exploitation, thus legitimizing precarious forms of hiring and labor management by presenting them as inexorable.

This last argument ultimately encourages and is encouraged by the idea that the class structure has changed with the emergence of the new precariat class or the emergence of a “gray zone” in the labor market. Although these theoretical propositions are presented from different political perspectives, both argue that there has been a general reduction in salaried work, which has been replaced by other types of work or even by other classes.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The proposal presented by the World Bank, influenced by the ideas advocated by Human Capital Theory, broadly suggests that the problem of unemployment, caused by the adoption of new production technologies, can be circumvented by measures that include education, technical training, and job skills. Contrary to this guidance, PNAD data on the insertion of workers into the Brazilian labor market between 2001 and 2015, viewed from the perspective of years of study, showed that the Brazilian workforce as a whole, although it had raised its educational credentials, did not have

guaranteed most workers a better position in this social context.

This reality can be seen as an opportunity to reflect on the role of education in shaping the social beings that make up the working class in Brazil. If today its effects are far from what was originally expected (greater well-being for workers), what alternatives exist to achieve the goal of improving the population's quality of life through work?

Based on this reality, it is possible to identify the need to rethink the social functions of the educational process, raising the final question of reflecting on the extent to which education is being designed with the almost sole purpose of training people for the world of work, to the detriment of training them to be social beings who, in addition to working in the production of goods and the provision of services, must also play an active social and political role. What if, instead of being seen exclusively as working individuals, each possessing a share of human capital that should be a source of income through work, we were to observe the collective of interdependent human beings?

From this perspective, in addition to technical training, wouldn't it be important for the population to have the opportunity to develop, in the formal educational process, from the early years of education, a critical understanding of their historical process of social formation? Of the way in which the society to which they belong is organized in order to reproduce itself? Of the effects on society itself of this form of reproduction of social life?

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